

DRUGS & FINE CHEMICALS

FDA Regulations Pending on Iron, Diet Supplement Product Levels

Industry is braced for the outcome of pending Food & Drug Administration regulations that could bring substantial effects on the food supplement market. Possible restrictions affecting some diet supplement products and proposals to double the amount of iron in enriched flour products are the two areas of current industry concern. If actions materialize in favor of increasing the amount of iron in food products, the eight to ten milligrams a pound requirement would be increased to about eighteen milligrams per pound. An FDA source commented last week that an internal decision is not targeted for a specific date, but that a public statement may be expected within the next three months.

FDA's decision will be partly based on a report the agency contracted to assist them in their decision. The assignment was given to Life Sciences Office of the Federation of American Society for Experimental Biology to review current industry practices and their products' effectiveness.

FDA's decision to review this area was prompted by last year's recommendations by the American Medical Association and the Food & Nutrition Board of the National Academy of Sciences. On February 15 of this year, reviews were invited for comment and revision, which touched off a debate that may, as some sources reported, affect FDA's final decision.

During this period of comment, an FDA source reported that no less than 500 comments were received from physicians and hematologists who expressed their views as to the risk of increased iron fortification in foods.

Those rejecting the proposed iron increase base their contention on the adverse effects of iron excesses on people with genetic defects, whose bodies are "predestined" to store excessive amounts of iron.

The iron that is given to foods as enrichment is in the form of medicinal iron, such as ferrous sulfate or ferrous salts. And the greatest danger, these doctors report, is that one can unwittingly consume an excess of iron, since signs of iron poisoning may not show up for thirty to sixty years.

Those warning the FDA as to the risks involved also pointed out that doubling the allowable iron could create danger from a little publicized disease known as hemochromatosis.

Taking the strongest position in favor of increased iron use has been the Council of Foods and Nutrition of the AMA. The Council expressed its recommendation as a national public health measure, particularly as a nutritional benefit to women of child-bearing age and children to correct or prevent iron deficiency anemia.

According to one source, those who are citing risks based on people with organic dysfunctions "are creating a distorted situation," because it is clear, he asserted, that a far greater percentage of the population is in need of additional iron in their diets.

The second issue affecting industry will be regulations on standards of identity presently used in dietary supplements. Fifty to seventy participants, comprised of supplement producers, consultants, and consumer groups have been giving testimony during a two-year long hearing between 1968 and 1970.

Based on their findings, an FDA source said last week that there may be a good number of products on the market whose ingredients do not qualify them to be advertised as dietary supplements. The whole purpose of this review, he said, is to rule out "irrational" products claims.

If finalized, regulations could be passed very shortly, according to last week's comments, adversely or favorably affecting a whole range of sizes, forms, and compositions of nutrient products.

"RDA," or "Recommended Daily Allowance," would replace MDR labeling, in FDA's desire to better inform consumers. Whether this would in turn effect an increase of some vitamins' use is highly speculative, asserted an FDA source. He explained that the impact would run in

THE WEEK'S PRICE CHANGES

Ending August 4, 1972

ADVANCED			
None			
REDUCED			
Silver bullion, ingots, .7c. per lb.			
Silver cyanide, 80% Ag, .5c. per lb.			
Silver nitrate, ACS, .4c. per lb.			
COMPARATIVE PRICE INDEXES (100=1959 average)			
Last Week	Prev. Week	Last Month	Aug. 6, 1971
80.77	80.77	80.76	80.76

For Current Prices See Page 26

different directions, depending on the nature of the products. Some products have been reviewed as containing excesses of certain supplement materials, while others, he said, have been found to contain too little.

Adding fuel to the Washington review of presently inadequate daily requirement listings is the representation of groups who are calling for complete elimination of requirement listings, contending that no regulatory agency should dictate requirements.

Apomorphine Hydrochloride—Supplies are still described as ample. Last week, sources listed single 5-ounce bottles at \$86 per ounce, two 5-ounce bottles at \$85.50, and five 5-ounce bottles at \$85 per ounce. This NF material is used as an emetic for poisoning. Described as an unstable and sensitive chemical, apomorphine hydrochloride is produced under strict, controlled conditions, and as such, is a modest item.

Ascorbic Acid—Two factors may reportedly affect the ascorbic acid market. Current debate in Washington to alter the "Minimum Daily Requirement" structure in vitamin products, and Roche Chemical Division's scheduled ascorbic plant scheduled for next year could impact availability and pricing, according to comments from trade sources and ascorbic producers last week.

The Washington factor, emphasized as highly speculative, could nevertheless materialize into a growth in some food fortification areas, including an increased demand for Vitamin C. The change would come in the wake of a current period when ascorbic acid producers are experiencing an ease off of last year's pressure to have supplies keep up with demand (Chem Marketing 7/17/72, page 15).

Though traditional end uses of ascorbic acid—in food fortification and pharmaceuticals—have remained constant, "we are still experiencing the residue of Linus Pauling publicity," one producer commented. While that unprecedented impact on the market has eased, no sources say there are very substantial inventories of spot material.

What could lift this slight pressure that some sources expect would be the multi-million pound expansion of production facilities at Hoffman-La Roche, tentatively planned to be on stream by January, 1973.

Trade sources estimate capacity would be 10 million kilos a year. Total US production in 1971, 11.7 million pounds, is about half this new plant's potential, if the 10 million figure is accurate.

However, this would depend on timing. One source explained that if the plant is operating by the time increased demand occurs, if it does occur, then demands will be met. But an exact target date for the ascorbic plant is still unconfirmed.

And speculations that the next move for ascorbic acid prices will be down is also uncertain. One producer suggested that initial costs for the plant along with an increase in demand could possibly lead to a rise in prices, while others suggest a decline in prices when the new facility comes into play.

One trade source familiar with the

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HEAVY & AGRICULTURAL CHEMICALS

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A Total of 759M Tons in 1976
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Dr. B. N. Stuckey

Dr. D. H. Benton

EASTMAN'S DPI DIVISION RESHAPED: Dr. C. H. Benton, Jr., has been appointed manager of sales development and technical service as a result of a reorganization of the DPI Division of Eastman Chemical Products.

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